

Pest management and control DISEASES

Relative humidity and nematode number and survival in rice seeds

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Seeds of rice varieties infested with nematode *D. angustus* were collected in Dong Thanp and Hau-Giang Province (the Mekong Delta) and soaked in dis-

tilled water for 2 hours. Then, the husk was separated from the albumen and seeds were resoaked for 1 hour.

Nematodes were found inside filled and unfilled grains, between the tegmen and albumen. They also can cling outside the tegmen.

Nematode populations in the seeds varied with variety of rice. Two-day-old seeds of local varieties Nep mua and Lua Tieu with 16.5-17% relative humid-

ity were examined. In Lua Tieu, nematode counts were 7 nematodes/ 100 unfilled grains and 25/ 100 filled grains. In Nep mua, nematode count was higher, 63 nematodes/ 100 unfilled grains and 167/100 filled grains.

When infested seeds were dried in the sun (44-45° C) for 4 days (6 hours/ day), seed humidity decreased to below 12% and nematodes were killed. ■

Fungicidal control of rice grain discoloration

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Yellow or brown discoloration of grain is caused by fungi — *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, and *Curvularia lunata*. Seven fungicides — carbendazim, Baycar, mancozeb, 34% mancozeb, IBP, edifenphos, and quaza-

tine — were tested for control of grain discoloration. Kannagi was the test variety.

Panicles at the milk stage were sprayed with spore suspensions of *H. oryzae*, *T. padwickii*, and *C. lunata*. After 24 hours, they were sprayed with the fungicides. Percentage discoloration was calculated at panicle maturity.

Application of 0.2% quazatine, IBP, and mancozeb prevented discoloration in the field (see table). Baycar and carbendazim were not effective. ■

Fungicidal control of grain discoloration at Mettupalayam, India.

Fungicide	Application rate (%)	Discolored grain ^a (%)
Carbendazim	0.2	4.1
Baycar	0.2	3.2
Mancozeb	0.2	0.3
34% mancozeb	0.2	0.2
IBP	0.2	0.3
Edifenphos	0.2	2.8
Quazatine	0.2	0.2
Control	—	8.7
CD (0.05) = 0.097		

^aMean of 3 replications.

Epidemiology of brown spot disease of rice in Karnataka, India

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The development and spread of brown spot disease were studied in the field and the relationship between disease incidence and weather factors was examined.

Highly susceptible rice variety Binnybhog was sown monthly, from 1 January to 31 December 1980 at Mandya. Periodic observations of disease development were made and daily maximum and minimum temperatures, relative humidity at 0730 hours and 1430 hours, rainfall, and sunshine were averaged for each month.

Incidence of brown spot was 2.5% from January to September, then suddenly increased to 45% during October, peaked at 50% in November, and dropped gradually to 40% in December (see table). The variability in disease incidence might be attributed to weather

factors. October to December had maximum temperatures of 27-29° C and minimum temperatures of 15-20° C, relative humidity of 86-90 at 0730 hours and 58-62 at 1430 hours, 0.2-2.6 mm rainfall, and average daily sunshine of 7-9 hours. ■

Weather factors and brown spot disease incidence at Mandya, Karnataka, India.

Month	Brown spot incidence (%)	Weather factors (av)					
		Temperature (°C)		Relative humidity		Sunshine/day (h)	
		Max	Min	0730 h	1430 h		
Jan	2	30	14	81	47	0	10
Feb	3	31	19	85	41	0	12
Mar	3	32	20	82	44	0	12
Apr	3	34	22	82	43	0	10
May	1	32	22	81	51	2.5	10
June	3	31	21	89	60	2.9	10
Jul	5	29	20	86	62	2.7	8
Aug	5	28	20	89	66	4.4	6
Sep	5	28	20	91	65	11.0	8
Oct	45	29	20	90	60	2.6	7
Nov	50	28	20	87	62	1.2	9
Dec	40	27	15	86	58	0.2	8